

A Study of Internet Usage by Secondary School Students

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Abstract

The internet has become an enormous part of people's daily lives. Over the last decades, internet connectivity has improved tremendously and it is easily available everywhere such as homes, offices, travels and schools. Today, empirical studies report that access to information can influence the academic performance of students. The present study on internet usage by secondary school students of Bareilly district was conducted on 250 students selected randomly from secondary schools located in Bareilly District of Uttar Pradesh. The data was collected by Internet Usage Scale developed by Shaloo Saini & Prof. Parminder Kaur. This scale consists of 20 items. Collected data was analysed using statistical technique such as mean, standard deviation and t-test. The study revealed that there is significant difference between the internet usages of U.P. Board student & C.B.S.E. Board student and U. P. Board boys & girls. But no significant difference was found C.B.S.E. Board boys & girls.

Keywords- Internet, Secondary school students.

Introduction:

Since the emergence of the internet, it has become an important medium of communication as well as a research and leisure tool. The growth of the Internet in the world provides many opportunities to many people around the world in many different ways. The wide access to digital technologies improves people's lives and provides great opportunities. When educational aspect of the internet use is considered, it is obvious that student, or people in general, who look for information can access it easily and with low cost. It is evident that the internet is a source of enormous information that anything can quickly and easily be reached. When students are considered, the use of the Internet is mainly for social and entertainment purposes. However, it is very obvious that the Internet provides not only social connection and entertainment, but also academic and scientific information as well. Additionally, the Internet can be used as a tool to learn the latest news all around the world as well as getting any kind of information that serves different purposes such as learning more information about a hobby or health. In the light of the above information, it is vitally important to encourage students to use this invaluable source to get any kind of information they need in their academic studies.

The number of internet users is continuously on the rise and it touched 3.8 billion in March 2017 as per the report of World Internet Users and Population Stats, 2017. Students show high percentage of internet users as compared to general public. Internet users in India were about 10% in 2011 which raised to 26 % in 2015. The percentage is expected to increase due to the Digital India Campaign launched by the government of India in 2015 with the initiative to increase the internet connectivity throughout India. According to Sharma etc. (2016) Internet addiction was found in more than one fourth of student. Duration of exposure of internet use, age at onset of starting internet use, rate of internet use etc more important role

in developing internet addiction. Internet is increasing so the internet addiction seems to rise in future. So interactive activities such as chatting over social networking sites and gaming are the key factors that may influence problematic internet use it should be under control. Mir & Paray (2018) conduct study secondary school students in Kashmir. According to study significant difference between male internet user and female internet user secondary school students on academic achievement & there was no significant difference between government and private secondary school students on academic achievement. Anwar (2014) results has also shown that internet usage pattern of male students is quite higher than the female students. It was found that average to high use of internet positively influenced the academic achievements while no use and extremely high usage had a negative impact on academic achievements of the students.

Significance of the study:

In 1990s debates on the effects of the internet use among secondary schools students were the business of the day. In some parts of the world, parents, teachers and communities at large were against the uses of the internet in schools. The notion against the internet uses in schools was triggered with the assumptions that the technologies were new to teachers, lack of know-how among related to accessing the internet itself. However the internet uses among schools students whether at home or schools increased dramatically. High computer, smart phones ownership, and household internet connectivity rates have increased internet use among secondary school students (Chen, Hsiao, Chen & Chen, 2014). Studies have reported that has either a negative influence or no significant influences on student learning performance or other outcomes (Davis, 2001); Kandell, 1998; Odaci, 2011; Odaci & Kalkan, 2010; Widyanto & Griffiths, 2006; Young, 1996). However, another study by Odaci (2011), found that there is no statistically significant relationship between problematic internet use and academic procrastination. Many factors have been in place to determine the inconsistent of the results including, generational factors generational differences, the available applications, the internet usage tasks, and the research tools used (Chen, Hsiao, Chen & Chen 2014). That is not all internet usage is of benefits to students and all people all the time, for example, pornography use and excessive chat among secondary students has a relatively negative effect on their academic success and life after schools.

Objective of the study:

1. To study the internet usage of UP Board & CBSE Board secondary school students.
2. To study the internet usage of Boys & Girls of UP Board secondary school students.
3. To study the internet usage of Boys & Girls of CBSE Board secondary school students.
4. To study the internet usage of UP Board Boys & CBSE Board Boys secondary school students.
5. To study the internet usage of UP Board Girls & CBSE Board Girls secondary school students.

Hypothesis:

1. There is no significant difference in internet usage of UP Board & CBSE Board secondary school students.
2. There is no significant difference in internet usage Boys & Girls of UP Board secondary school students.
3. There is no significant difference in internet usage Boys & Girls of CBSE Board secondary school students.
4. There is no significant difference in internet usage of UP Board Boys & CBSE Board Boys secondary school students.

5. There is no significant difference in internet usage of UP Board Girls & CBSE Board Girls secondary school students.

Delimitation of the study:

The study was delimited to secondary school students in UP Board and CBSE Board located in Bareilly district of Uttar Pradesh state only.

Methodology:

The investigator randomly selected students from secondary schools located in Bareilly of Uttar Pradesh state. The sample comprised of 125 UP Board school students (Boys and Girls) and 125 CBSE Board school students (Boys and Girls). Survey method was used for data collection. Internet Usage Scale developed by Shaloo Saini & Prof. Parminder Kaur was used to collect data from sample student of secondary schools of Bareilly. The questionnaire consists of 20 items. The data were analysed using statistical techniques such as mean, standard deviation and t-ratio.

Interpretation of data

- H1. There is no significant difference internet usage of UP Board & CBSE Board secondary school students.

Testing of Hypothesis 1.

S a m p l e n	M	D	T value calculated	Level of significance	Critical value of t - R a t i o	
UP Board Student	125	42.312	-8.48	- 3 . 5 4	. 0 5	1 . 9 7
CBSE Board Student	125	5 0 . 8			S i g n i f i c a n t	(at df = 248)

Result/ Conclusion:

Hypothesis 1 tests the scores of UP Board students and CBCE Board students toward the usage of internet. After the analysis of data with mean, standard deviation and t-test, it can be explore that, significance deference is detected between UP board and CBSE board students' toward internet usage because calculated t-value is greater than the critical value of t-ratio at .05 level of significance. So the null hypothesis is rejected. The t-value falls at -3.54, and it indicate that the usage of internet of CBSE board students is greater than UP board students. CBSE board student more use the internet than UP board student due to their economic condition and availability of internet facilities in the school.

2. H1. There is no significant difference in internet usage of Boys & Girls of UP Board's secondary school students.

Testing of Hypothesis 2.

S a m p l e	n	M	D	T v a l u e calculated	Level of significance	Critical value of t - R a t i o
UP Board Boys	60	37.85	-8.58	- 4 . 0 4	. 0 5	2 . 6 3
UP Board Girls	65	46.34			S i g n i f i c a n t	(at df = 123)

Result/ conclusion

Hypothesis 2 tests the scores of UP Board boys students and UP Board girls students toward the usage of internet. After the analysis of data with mean, standard deviation and t-test, it can be explore that, significance deference is detected between UP board boys and girls students' toward internet usage because calculated t-value is greater than the critical value of t-ratio at .05 level of significance. So the null hypothesis is rejected. The t-value falls at -4.04, and it indicate that the usage of internet of UP board girls students is greater than UP board boys students. UP board boys use more internet than UP board girls because the boys remains free from home responsibilities and household work but girls involve in house tasks.

3. H3. There is no significant difference in internet usage of Boys & Girls of CBSE Board secondary school students.

Testing of Hypothesis 3.

S a m p l e	N	M	D	T v a l u e calculated	Level of significance	Critical value of t - R a t i o
CBSE Board boys S t u d e n t	60	48.65	-4.13	- 1 . 8 7	. 0 5	2 . 6 3
CBSE Board girls S t u d e n t	65	52.78			Non Significant	(at df = 122.55)

Results/conclusion

Hypothesis 3 tests the scores of CBSE Board boys students and CBSE Board girls students toward the usage of internet. After the analysis of data with mean, standard deviation and t-test, it can be explore that, no significance deference is detected between CBSE board boys and girls students' toward internet usage because calculated t-value is lesser than the critical value of t-ratio at .05 level of significance. So the null hypothesis is accepted. The t-value falls at -1.87, and it indicate that the usage of internet of CBSE board boys and girls students is equal. The boys and girls student of CBSE have equal level of computer and internet knowledge because both the groups used internet, computer lab, technological communication equally.

4. H4. There is no significant difference in internet usage of UP Board Boys & CBSE Board Boys of secondary school students.

Testing of Hypothesis 4.

S a m p l e n	M	D	T value calculated	Level of significance	Critical value of t - R a t i o	
UP Board boys	65	46.43	-6.35	- 2 . 8 6	. 0 5	2 . 6 3
CBSE Board boys	65	52.78		Significant	(at df = 126.97)	

Result/ conclusion

Hypothesis 4 tests the scores of UP Board boys students and CBSE Board boys students toward the usage of internet. After the analysis of data with mean, standard deviation and t-test, it can be explore that, significance deference is detected between UP board and CBSE board boys students' toward internet usage because calculated t-value is greater than the critical value of t-ratio at .05 level of significance. So the null hypothesis is rejected. The t-value falls at -2.86, and it indicate that the usage of internet of CBSE board boys students is greater than UP board boys students. CBSE board boys are more aware than UP board boys towards the usage of internet because CBSE board school have facility of computer lab and certain computer book in the curriculum.

5. H5. There is no significant difference in internet usage of UP Board Girls & CBSE Board Girls secondary school students.

Testing of Hypothesis 5.

S a m p l e n	M	D	T value calculated	Level of significance	Critical value of t - R a t i o	
UP Board girls	60	37.85	-10.8	- 5 . 1 1	. 0 5	2 . 6 3
CBSE Board girls	60	48.65		Significant	(at df = 118)	

Result / conclusion

Hypothesis 5 tests the scores of UP Board girls students and CBSE Board girls students toward the usage of internet. After the analysis of data with mean, standard deviation and t-test, it can be explore that, significance deference is detected between UP board girls and CBSE board girls students' toward internet usage because calculated t-value is greater than the critical value of t-ratio at .05 level of significance. So the null hypothesis is rejected. The t-value falls at -10.8, and it indicate that the usage of internet of CBSE board girls students is greater than UP board girls students. CBSE board girls have more knowledge of internet usage then UP board girls because the curriculum of CBSE board contain the books of computers, internet and computer labs also.

Chart 1. Mean score of various groups

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